

Explorations In Augmented String Instrument Design: A Conversation With Mentors Of Musical Innovation

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ABSTRACT

The EV is a 3D-printed augmented stringed instrument that combines the acoustic string and a digital synthesizer through convolution. Its development reflects David Wessel's thoughts on instrument design, emphasizing embodied musical creation, responsiveness and detailed control, and the investigation of new musical languages. The instrument's evolution balances intentional design with unexpected discoveries, shaping its unique sonic identity. Mentors and the interplay between the EV's development and compositional practice play a crucial role in its ongoing refinement and creative potential.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the advent of digital music creation, composers, performers, and builders have grappled with numerous methodologies to integrate these technologies into live performance. The approaches explored through experimental instruments reflected the perspectives and musical visions of their builders. David Wessel, informed by his interdisciplinary background in mathematics, psychology, and computer music, offered poignant insight into the design and performance of electronic instruments, emphasizing responsiveness, nuance, and the embodiment of musical expression.

1.1 Augmented Strings Contextualized

Dozens of augmented stringed instruments have been developed over the past few decades; the interests and perspectives of their builders found expression both in these string experiments and across various projects throughout their careers. As an engineer, Max Mathews often explored the translation of familiar Western music paradigms to nascent digital ecosystems: Music N's architecture reflected that of a score and instrument; the Radio-Baton was conceived to "provide new ways for interpreting and performing traditional scores" [1]; and the Electronic Violin investigated the potential of electronic resonance to serve as a rival of—or even a substitute for—traditional acoustic violins [2].

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Through his art, Suguru Goto explored concepts of virtualization and transhumanism. The SuperPalm, one of his earlier projects, completely virtualizes the violin's sound production: having no strings or a traditional bow, sensors and buttons map the gestures of the player to a computer synthesizer equipped with a behavior-tracking neural network [3]. His later work navigates similar themes, exemplified by his sound-generating body suits that explored the relationship between the performer and digital avatars—at times, the human controlled the avatar, and at others, the avatar controlled the human [4].

David Wessel's perspectives on the embodiment of musical expression and the importance of responsiveness in controllers are evident in his work on the Slabs [5], a touchpad-based controller that surpassed the resolution and sensitivity of its contemporaries; the Augmented Cello [6], an electric cello with extended control capabilities; and the Open Sound Control protocol [7], a tool that significantly expanded the possibilities for networked music. Through his creative work, mentorship, and research, Wessel developed an intricate framework for musical instrument design that emphasized the interplay between physical gesture, sound, and cognitive engagement. Many aspects of this framework lie at the foundation of the EV, particularly its grounding in embodied music cognition and the interplay between instrument design and composition. This paper explores the instrument's design philosophy through three interrelated lenses: embodied music creation, expressive sound as both control and output, and instrument design as a musical language.

2. EV FRAMEWORK

2.1 Overview

The EV (the name evolved from electronic viola or violin) [8] is a 3D-printed stringed instrument, with no resonating cavity. At 16", it is the size of a viola. Different tuning systems have been experimented with, including cello, viola, and viola with octave-down A and D strings. The instrument uses a quad infrared pickup for the four strings; the signals are pre-amplified and then digitized using a Bela single-board computer. The Bela transmits the string data via USB to a laptop running Pure Data (Pd). A patch interprets the data and synthesizes sound based on user-defined parameters. Unlike other augmented stringed instruments which employ additional sensors (such as buttons and knobs) for control, the EV considers the notion

that the *sound is the interface*, as described by Agostino Di Scipio [9]. While this may be considered an objective constraint [10], the intent is to allow the player to focus solely on the physical movements of traditional string performance (rather than extended control mechanisms). As a result, the EV is readily playable by a classically trained violinist or violist. Although the instrument has a solid body, the string vibration can still be felt through it, giving the player a sensation similar to that of an acoustic instrument. Lastly, it uses a standard bow.

2.2 Embodied Musical Creation

David Wessel believed that, although the cognition of music is a mental activity, the mind is deeply informed by ‘the way the body interacts with the world’ [11]. In a 2013 lecture at UC Berkeley’s ParLab, he outlined four design criteria for new musical instruments: bodily engagement, musically expressive and inspiring, easy to play at the entry level, but accepting of lifelong development of virtuosity. He emphasized ‘bodily engagement’ as the main criterion [12].

The initial inspiration for the EV emerged in the final years of my undergraduate studies in viola performance in 2004–2005. My fascination with electronic music prompted me to take classes with Allan Schindler at the Eastman Computer Music Center. While the possibilities of sound synthesis were compelling, I sought a path to integrate my passion for the viola and the rich expressive palette I was striving to develop under my viola teacher, John Graham. Graham’s holistic approach to viola performance posited that the technical mechanisms of execution and the essentials of musicality shared the same core: the pulse of the music. Though challenging to achieve, my progress within this framework enabled me to experience viola playing in a more visceral and satisfying way than before. Driven by a desire to bring this depth of experience to my electronic music practice, I began incorporating the viola as a controller in various capacities. Through this process, I began to appreciate the power and influence of embodied musical creation.

Visually, the physical act of performance can communicate additional dimensions of meaning to the audience. Until the electronic age, physical input was necessary for sonic result, with the force of attack often in direct correlation to the intensity and timbral quality of the resulting sound. Generally, much of the way we listen is interwoven with these expectations, or as Wessel described “we hear in accord with hypotheses that we have about the world” [11]. The field of embodied music cognition investigates the relationship by which the body translates its perception of the physical world to the mental level while simultaneously enacting its mental processes upon the physical environment through action. This system serves as a lynchpin in music creation and experience as described by Marc Leman: “This two-way mediation process is largely constrained by body movements, which are assumed to play a central role in all musical activities. The embodied music cognition approach assumes that the (musical) mind results from this embodied interaction with music.” [13] My own experience acknowledges this two-way process: as a performer, I’m aware that my bodily presence is interwoven with the audience’s experience of the music, and, as an

audience member, I have a somatic understanding of the music via the embodied performer.

In my compositional work with the EV, the opportunity to bring a piece from the studio to the stage is an invigorating experience whereby the musical narrative that had previously existed only in my mind is brought to life and shared both sonically and physically with the audience.

2.3 Sensors and Nuance: The Sound Is The Interface

According to Wessel, detailed and responsive sensors are essential in computer music performance (as evidenced in the Slabs) and lamented the music industry’s “insistence on standard keyboard controllers” [14]. For example, he argued that rather than defaulting to triggers for creating event onsets, amplitude should often be treated as a continuous parameter. Further, rather than resort to the use of knobs, other control methods should be investigated in order to enable the shaping of each individual note [15], from complete silence through the full dynamic range. Though some augmented stringed instruments, such as Goto’s SuperPalm, completely replaced the bow/string mechanism in favor of other control interfaces, the EV embraces it as a high-fidelity control source for the subtle shaping of electronic sound.

From the beginning, the purpose of the EV was to meld the seemingly infinite expressive detail of string playing with the sonic vastness of electronic music. In a way, each discipline lacked what the other offered: the limitations of MIDI-based control interfaces paled in contrast to the nuance of the viola, yet the possibilities of the digital palette were far broader than the viola’s single sound source. Considering this, a central goal in the EV’s development was to preserve the expressive potential of the acoustic viola. Early experiments used the acoustic signal’s pitch and amplitude to control a software synthesizer; the output was then vocoded with the original acoustic sound. The result resembled a synthesizer but retained the pitch, amplitude, and spectral nuance of the viola. Later work fully implemented FFT convolution algorithms to achieve a similar effect. This approach echoes Di Scipio’s investigations into extracting data from sound to be used as control signals [9]. In the EV’s context, each frequency bin of the FFT analysis acts as a control source, subtly shaping the timbre of the synthesizer in accordance with the expressive detail in the musician’s performance.

2.4 Instrument Design as Musical Language

In a 1999 interview, Wessel spoke of instrument design in relation to jazz musicians developing their own musical language, concluding that “computer musicians could do that kind of thing, simply because they were required to almost invent their instrument from the ground up”; he believed this to be an important “ethic in aesthetic” in orienting our musical pursuits [16]. This resonates with my work with the EV: design choices made during its (hardware and software) development have afforded creativity and experimentation, with each unique element expanding the instrument’s sonic possibilities. Over this exploration, the instrument’s sound and musical lexicon have come into focus. Mentorship, practical use, and experimentation have all been invaluable with each incremental

development contributing to its language.

Figure 1. EV 1 with boxes housing a preamplifier and Arduino ADC.

3. ORIGINS

Fifteen years after my initial experiments, I began developing the EV in Doug Geers’s *Building Electronic Musical Instruments* class at Brooklyn College. The EV 1 (see Figure 1), an acoustic viola retrofitted with conductive sensors under the fingerboard and a quadraphonic magnetic coil pickup, transmitted eight signals via a preamplifier and Arduino to a laptop running Pd [17]. My first compositional sketch paired the EV with a string trio, using the EV to control an FM synthesizer. When I presented it to my composition teacher, Morton Subotnick, he asked, “Brian, why are you going to all the trouble to design a new instrument if you are going to make it sound just like something that’s already been done?” He encouraged me, “What if you rethought this instrument so that it could produce sounds that no other instrument would have the capability of?” I realized I had overlooked my earlier experiments in vocoding synthesized and acoustic signals. Connecting four auxiliary outputs from the preamplifier to my laptop’s ADC, I constructed three convolution algorithms (two taken from published sources, and one of my own) each producing a distinct sound when combined with the FM synth. This marked the beginning of the EV’s distinct sound palette.

A software-based mixer in Pd enabled selective bussing of FM synth sound to convolution algorithms, whose outputs were mixed to varying degrees. A control voltage (CV) matrix linked each string’s amplitude envelope to synthesizer parameters. Though simple in concept, this configuration created a robust sonic palette reflecting the EV’s acoustic string subtleties. This iteration was used to compose *Etudes & Vignettes* [18], a suite of six movements exploring the instrument’s sonic potential. The composition’s sound, while clearly electronic, retained the character of an acoustic string and the unpredictability of human performance. For instance, the pizzicato notes of ‘Etude 4’ have the spectral envelope of a plucked string but with a synthesizer’s timbre. In ‘Vignette 1,’ the EV’s sonority resembles a wind instrument, combining the brightness of an octave-up synthesizer with the A string’s spectrum. The oddly timbered tremolo and synthetic pizzicato sound give the movement an eerie quality. A preset management system was later added for live performance of the work [19].

The majority of developments in the EV’s language have been intentional; however, shortcomings in my own hardware and software design have also presented unexpected creative opportunities. The first movement of *Nuages* [20], my subsequent work for the EV, opens with an unusual

drone. EV 1 suffered from significant noise, possibly caused by the homemade pickup and preamp—a CD4049 inverter circuit tightly packed into a wire-filled box. When the instrument was connected, the system’s noise was processed through the software engine’s settings, creating a distinctive sonic texture. With prominent static and noise, yet a subdued resonance and machine-like purring, the sound proved compelling and was used to open the movement. Also contributing to this sound’s quality was an FFT convolution algorithm of my own design. Early in the EV’s software development, its two algorithms had been sourced from online and published materials. In the spirit of experimentation, I attempted to design my own algorithm. Though poorly implemented—the FFT window envelopes were audible and the convolution element failed to convincingly convolve the two sources—the results were unique and added contrast to the EV’s palette. While hardware improvements removing much of the noise, this FFT convolution algorithm remains integral to many compositions.

Figure 2. EV 2 with a box housing a preamplifier and Bela ADC.

To better accommodate onboard sensors, a 3D-printed body was designed for the EV. The EV 2 (see Figure 2) underwent repeated hardware and software iterations, gaining features such as two additional synthesizers, a spectral centroid control source for the CV matrix, grain delay, reverb, and a buffer freeze feature for each mixer channel. Matrix destinations were added to control parameters within these modules. A major software overhaul introduced independent parameter settings for each string, effectively quadrupling sound output potential. The mixing engine was redesigned to support third-order ambisonic encoding and decoding, moving beyond mono output [21]. Each new module combined custom design features with canonical digital signal processing concepts. For example, the buffer freeze, based on the PaulStretch algorithm, can refresh its buffer upon completing a cycle, creating a semi-frozen convolved string sound.

This configuration culminated in *Daughter of the Stars* [22][23], where the EV’s sonic palette expanded upon the language established in *Etudes & Vignettes*. For instance, the thematic melody uses a pitched-up synthesizer convolved with the EV’s string. However, the phase distortion synthesizer attenuates upper frequencies of its sawtooth wave, resulting in a less strident timbre than the woodwind-like melody in *Etudes & Vignettes*. The buffer freeze further expands the EV’s vocabulary: the opening low F# sonority is created by routing a wet-only synthesizer to the reverb, which is buffer-frozen in refresh mode. This frozen sound is also sent to the grain delay, with its output panned separately within the ambisonic dome.

The EV’s creative lexicon has also expanded through the

use of its software engine as an external signal processor, a capability often valued in analog and digital synthesizers (e.g., the Korg MS-20). Applying the EV's processing to other sound sources has produced compelling results. For instance, *experiments from n-space* processes HYPERCUBE, a quartet of saxophone, guitar, piano, and percussion. Rather than interfacing with the EV's strings, the four processing engines are assigned to each instrument, adapting the EV's sonic identity and language to a new context.

In reflection, much of my compositional output over the past four years has been intricately tied to the development of the EV. The instrument's evolving language is evident throughout my work, just as my own language as a composer has, in turn, been reflexively embedded into the EV.

4. CONCLUSION

The development of the EV is a continual interplay between instrument design, performance, and composition. Reflecting insights of David Wessel—embodied musical creation, responsiveness and detailed control, and the investigation of new musical languages—the instrument's design encourages the exploration of both nuance in string performance and the vast potential of electronic sound, resulting in a unique sonic palette. Ultimately, the EV explores a new paradigm in augmented string design, where the boundaries between acoustic and electronic realms fuse, offering a platform for the composition and performance of new electroacoustic music.

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